

FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF LOCAL DELAMINATIONS INDUCED BY ANGLE PLY MATRIX CRACKING IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Costas Soutis*, Maria Kashtalyan** and Paul T Curtis⁺

*Aerospace Engineering, The University of Sheffield, UK

**School of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Aberdeen, UK

+Materials and Structures, DSTL Farnborough, UK

ABSTRACT

Delamination is a commonly observed failure mode in continuous fibre-reinforced composite laminates subjected to static or fatigue tensile loading. Its initiation is often triggered by matrix cracks, i.e. cracks in the resin running parallel to the fibres in the off-axis ply of the laminate, which result in high interlaminar stresses at the ply interface. In the present paper, local delaminations growing uniformly from the tips of matrix cracks in the inner ϕ -layer of a general symmetric $[(S)/\phi]_s$ laminate subjected to in-plane tensile loading are analysed. The strain energy release rates associated with such delaminations are predicted analytically using the Equivalent Constraint Model of the damaged laminate. Stress field in the damaged ply is determined from the analysis of a representative segment containing one crack and two crack tip delaminations by means of a 2-D shear lag method. Closed-form expressions for G_I^{ld} (Mode I contribution), G_{II}^{ld} (Mode II contribution) and the total G^{ld} strain energy release rates are derived, representing them as linear functions of the first partial derivatives of the degraded stiffness properties of the damaged ϕ -layer with respect to the delamination area. The expressions give strain energy release rates that depend both on the matrix crack density and delamination area. Their dependence on the matrix crack density, delamination area and ply orientation angle is examined both for balanced and unbalanced laminates. Comparison with the closed-form expression suggested by O'Brien is also made.

KEYWORDS: delamination, matrix cracking, strain energy release rate

INTRODUCTION

Initiation and accumulation of matrix cracks parallel to the fibres in the off-axis plies is the first stage of damage development in multidirectional composite laminates subjected to in-plane tensile loading. Matrix cracking reduces the laminate stiffness and strength and also triggers development of other harmful resin-dominated damage modes such as delaminations. Studies of delaminations induced by matrix cracks have been focusing predominantly on delaminations caused by matrix cracks in the 90° -plies [1-4]. In laminates with thicker 90° -plies, strip-shaped local delaminations initiating from crack tips and growing uniformly along the cracks were observed. O'Brien [5] suggested a simple closed-form expression for the strain energy release rate associated with such delaminations.

By comparison, delaminations growing from the tips of angle ply cracks have received considerably less attention. O'Brien and Hooper [6, 7] observed matrix crack induced delaminations in symmetric angle-ply $[0_2/\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminates under quasi-static and fatigue tensile loading ($\theta = 15^\circ; 20^\circ; 25^\circ; 30^\circ$). Delaminations occurred in the $(\theta/-\theta)$ interface, bounded by the cracks in the $(-\theta)$ -ply and the stress free edge. Closed form expressions for strain energy release rate were

derived on the basis of simple load shearing rules for uniform and partial local delaminations. As for the transverse crack tip delamination [5], strain energy release rate for uniform local delamination was independent of delamination size and matrix crack density, while for partial local delamination it depended on delamination length. However, when the matrix crack length and the corresponding delamination length along the free edge is small, the difference between the uniform and partial delamination solutions was found to be insignificant.

Salpekar and O'Brien [8] used a 3-D FE analysis to study matrix crack induced delaminations in $(0/\theta/-\theta)_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates loaded in tension. For $(0/45/-45)_s$ laminate, the strain energy release rate for uniform local delamination in the $(45/-45)$ interface, growing from the matrix crack in the (-45°) -ply, was found to be higher near the laminate edge than in the interior of the laminate. Salpekar, O'Brien and Shivakumar [9] computed strain energy release rates associated with partial local delaminations originating from matrix cracks and bounded by the free edge in $(0/\theta/-\theta)_s$ and $(\theta/-\theta/0)_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates using a 3-D FE method. The total strain energy release rate was calculated using three different techniques: the virtual crack closure technique, the equivalent domain integral technique, and a global energy balance technique. For both lay-ups analysed, the fraction of the total strain energy release rate associated with mode I was greatest near the matrix crack and decreased near the free edge. It also decreased with increasing delamination length and was influenced by matrix crack length. However, no comparison with O'Brien's [7] closed-form expressions for uniform and partial local delaminations was made.

The present paper is concerned with fracture mechanics analysis of matrix crack induced uniform local delaminations in general symmetric composite laminates loaded in tension. The approach employs the Equivalent Constraint Model (ECM) of the damaged laminate [10], earlier applied to $[\pm\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminates damaged by transverse cracking in the 90° plies and local delaminations growing uniformly from the matrix crack tips at the $(-\theta/90)$ interface [11] and to cross-ply $[0_m/90_n]_s$ laminates with delaminations growing along transverse cracks and splits [12, 13]. Figure 1 shows a schematic of a damaged $[S/\phi]_s$ laminate consisting of the inner ϕ -layer and outer sublaminates S and subjected to in-plane tensile loading. Matrix cracks in inner ϕ -layer are assumed to span the whole width of the laminate and be spaced uniformly at a distance $2s$. Local delaminations growing from the tips of matrix cracks at the (S/ϕ) interface are assumed to be strip-shaped, with a strip width 2ℓ . The laminate is referred to the global xyz and local $x_1x_2x_3$ co-ordinate systems, with the x_1 axis directed along the fibres in the ϕ -layer.

Figure 1. Plan and edge views of a $[S/\phi]_s$ laminate subjected to in-plane tensile loading and damaged by matrix cracks in the inner off-axis ply and local delaminations at the crack tips

CALCULATION OF STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE USING THE EQUIVALENT CONSTRAINT MODEL

The total strain energy release rate G^{ld} associated with local delaminations growing from the tips of matrix cracks is equal to the first partial derivative of the total strain energy U stored in the damaged laminate with respect to the total delamination area A^{ld} provided the applied strains $\{\bar{\varepsilon}\}$ are fixed and the matrix crack density $C = (2s)^{-1}$ remains unchanged

$$G^{ld} = -\left. \frac{\partial U}{\partial A^{ld}} \right|_{\{\bar{\varepsilon}\}, C} \quad (1)$$

The strain energy release rate can be effectively calculated using the Equivalent Constraint Model of the damaged laminate [10, 11]. In the global co-ordinates, the total strain energy stored in the laminate element with a finite gauge length L and width w is

$$U = \frac{wL}{2} \sum_k (z_k - z_{k-1}) (\{\bar{\varepsilon}\} + \{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{thermal}\} + \{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{hygro}\})^T [\bar{Q}]_k (\{\bar{\varepsilon}\} + \{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{thermal}\} + \{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{hygro}\}) \quad (2)$$

where $\{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{thermal}\}$ and $\{\bar{\varepsilon}_k^{hygro}\}$ are respectively residual thermal and residual hygroscopic strains in the laminate due to the temperature and moisture difference between the stress-free and actual state, and $[\bar{Q}]_k$ is the in-plane reduced stiffness matrix of layer k in the global co-ordinates.

The stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}]_\phi$ of the homogeneous layer, equivalent to the damaged one, is a function of the relative delamination area $D^{ld} = \ell/s$ and the relative crack density $D^{mc} = h_\phi/s$ (i.e. normalised by the thickness h_ϕ of the damaged ϕ -layer). The in-plane stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}]_\phi$ of the equivalent constraint layer in the global co-ordinates can be obtained from the in-plane stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}^{(\phi)}]$ in the local co-ordinates by the well-known transformation formulae [14]. The residual in-plane stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}^{(\phi)}]$ of the equivalent layer in the local co-ordinates is related to the in-plane stiffness matrix $[\hat{Q}^{(\phi)}]$ of the undamaged layer via the In-situ Damage Effective Functions (IDEFs) $\Lambda_{jj} = \Lambda_{jj}(D^{mc}, D^{ld})$, $j = 2, 6$ as

$$[\bar{Q}^{(\phi)}] = [\hat{Q}^{(\phi)}] - \begin{bmatrix} (\hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)})^2 / \hat{Q}_{22}^{(\phi)} \Lambda_{22} & \hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)} \Lambda_{22} & 0 \\ \hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)} \Lambda_{22} & \hat{Q}_{22}^{(\phi)} \Lambda_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \hat{Q}_{66}^{(\phi)} \Lambda_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Noting that the area of a single crack tip delamination is $a^{ld} = 2\ell w / |\sin \phi|$ (Fig. 1), the total delamination area is equal to

$$A^{ld} = 2a^{ld} CL = 2LwD^{ld} / |\sin \phi| \quad (4)$$

If hygrothermal effects are neglected, the strain energy release rate, calculated from Eqs. (1), (2) and (4), is

$$G^{ld}(\bar{\varepsilon}, D^{mc}, D^{ld}) = -\frac{h_\phi}{2} \{\bar{\varepsilon}\}^T \frac{\partial [\bar{Q}]_\phi}{\partial D^{ld}} \{\bar{\varepsilon}\} |\sin \phi| \quad (5)$$

Under uniaxial strain, Eq. (5) simplifies to

$$G^{ld}(\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}, D^{mc}, D^{ld}) = -\frac{h_\phi}{2} \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 \frac{\partial \bar{Q}_{xx,\phi}}{\partial D^{ld}} |\sin \phi| \quad (6)$$

Calculation of the residual in-plane axial stiffness $\bar{Q}_{xx,\phi}$ using Eq. (3) and the transformation formulae [14], yields the strain energy release rate associated with local delamination in terms of the In-situ Damage Effective Functions (IDEFs) $\Lambda_{22}, \Lambda_{66}$ and stiffness properties of the undamaged material $\hat{Q}_{ij}^{(\phi)}$ as

$$G^{ld}(\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}, D^{mc}, D^{ld}) = \frac{h_\phi}{2} \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 \left[\left(\frac{\hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)2}}{\hat{Q}_{22}^{(2)}} \cos^4 \phi + 2\hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)} \sin^2 \phi \cos^2 \phi + \hat{Q}_{22}^{(\phi)} \sin^4 \phi \right) \frac{\partial \Lambda_{22}}{\partial D^{ld}} + 4\hat{Q}_{66}^{(\phi)} \sin^2 \phi \cos^2 \phi \frac{\partial \Lambda_{66}}{\partial D^{ld}} \right] |\sin \phi| \quad (7)$$

The first partial derivatives of IDEFs that appear in Eq. (7) are explicit functions of the damage parameters D^{mc}, D^{ld} and can be calculated analytically.

MODE SEPARATION (MODES I AND II)

Damage development in the off-axis plies of general symmetric laminates always occurs under mixed mode conditions due to shear-extension coupling. It is therefore important in the calculation of the total strain energy release rate to be able to separate Mode I and Mode II contributions. For a $[(S)/\phi]_s$ laminate with damaged ϕ -layer modelled by an ‘equivalent’ laminate, the total strain energy release rate for crack tip uniform local delaminations is equal to the first partial derivative of the portion of the total strain energy stored in the ‘equivalent’ homogeneous layer with respect to damage area

$$G^{ld} = - \left. \frac{\partial U^{(\phi)}}{\partial A^{ld}} \right|_{\{\bar{\varepsilon}\}, C} \quad (8)$$

In the local co-ordinates (Fig. 1), this portion of the total strain energy can be separated into extensional and shear parts

$$U^{(\phi)} = U_I^{(\phi)} + U_{II}^{(\phi)} = Lwh_\phi (\bar{\sigma}_{11}^{(\phi)} \bar{\varepsilon}_{11}^{(\phi)} + \bar{\sigma}_{22}^{(\phi)} \bar{\varepsilon}_{22}^{(\phi)}) + Lwh_\phi \bar{\sigma}_{12}^{(\phi)} \bar{\gamma}_{12}^{(\phi)} \quad (9)$$

Under uniaxial strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}$, strains and stresses in the ‘equivalent’ homogeneous layer are

$$\begin{aligned} \{\bar{\varepsilon}^{(\phi)}\} &= \{\cos^2 \phi, \sin^2 \phi, 2 \cos \phi \sin \phi\}^T \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}, \\ \{\bar{\sigma}^{(\phi)}\} &= [\bar{Q}^{(2)}] \{\cos^2 \phi, \sin^2 \phi, 2 \cos \phi \sin \phi\}^T \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the modified stiffness matrix $[\bar{Q}^{(\phi)}]$ of the ‘equivalent’ homogeneous layer in the local co-ordinates is given by Eq. (3). Substitution of Eqs. (9), (10) and (4) into Eq. (8) gives Mode I and Mode II contributions into the total strain energy release rate as follows

$$G_1^{ld} = - \frac{\partial U_1^{(\phi)}}{\partial A^{ld}} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 f_1(D^{ld}) \quad (11a)$$

$$f_1(D^{ld}) = \frac{h_\phi}{2} \left(\frac{\hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)2}}{\hat{Q}_{22}^{(\phi)}} \cos^4 \phi + 2\hat{Q}_{12}^{(\phi)} \sin^2 \phi \cos^2 \phi + \hat{Q}_{22}^{(\phi)} \sin^4 \phi \right) \frac{\partial \Lambda_{22}}{\partial D^{ld}} |\sin \phi| \quad (11b)$$

$$G_{II}^{ld} = -\frac{\partial U_{II}^{(\phi)}}{\partial A^{ld}} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 f_2(D^{ld}), \quad f_2(D^{ld}) = 2h_\phi \hat{Q}_{66}^{(\phi)} \frac{\partial \Lambda_{66}}{\partial D^{ld}} \cos^2 \phi |\sin^3 \phi| \quad (12)$$

These expressions can be used with appropriate fracture criteria to estimate the onset of local delamination in an already cracked laminate. The resulting total strain energy release rate $G^{ld} = G_I^{ld} + G_{II}^{ld}$ coincides with Eq. (7).

DELAMINATION ONSET

The total strain energy release rate and its Mode I and Mode II contributions at the onset of delamination in an already cracked laminate can be evaluated from Eqs. (7), (11) and (12) by assuming $D^{ld} = 0$. Figure 2 shows predictions of the normalised total strain energy release rate $G^{ld} / \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ at the onset of local delamination ($D^{ld} = 0$) as a function of the crack density in the $(-\theta)$ -ply of carbon/epoxy AS4/3506-1 balanced $[0_2 / \theta_2 / -\theta_2]_s$ laminates. Lamina properties of the AS4/3506-1 graphite/epoxy material system are as follows [6, 7]: $E_{11}=135\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=11\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=5.8\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.301$, single ply thickness $t=0.124\text{mm}$. It can be seen that, for the same crack density, the normalised total strain energy release rate at the delamination onset is higher for greater values of θ , which will translate into lower onset strain value. For all ply orientation angles θ , total strain energy release rate at the delamination onset depends linearly on matrix crack density, slightly decreasing as the crack density increases. For instance, for the $[0_2 / 45_2 / -45_2]_s$ laminate the difference between the values of $G^{ld} / \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ at 0.5 cracks/cm and 5 cracks/cm is 8.5 %. Reduction in the normalised strain energy release rate value will translate into a decrease in the delamination onset strain in laminates with higher matrix crack density.

Figure 2. Normalised strain energy release rate $G^{ld} / \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ for uniform local delamination in a cracked balanced symmetric $[0_2 / \theta_2 / -\theta_2]_s$ AS4/3506-1 laminate as a function of crack density. Relative delamination area $D^{ld} = 0$ (onset of delamination), matrix crack density 2 cracks/cm

Figure 3. Normalised strain energy release rate $G^{ld} / \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ for uniform local delamination in a cracked unbalanced symmetric $[0_2 / \theta_2]_s$ AS4/3506-1 laminate as a function of crack density. Relative delamination area $D^{ld} = 0$ (onset of delamination), matrix crack density 2 cracks/cm

Figure 3 shows predictions of the normalised total strain energy release rate $G^{ld} / \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ at the onset of local delamination ($D^{ld} = 0$) as a function of the crack density in the θ -ply of AS4/3506-1 unbalanced $[0_2 / \theta_2]_s$ laminates. For all ply orientation angles θ , total strain energy release rate at the delamination onset depends linearly on matrix crack density, slightly decreasing as the crack density increases. This will translate into an increase in the delamination onset strain in laminates with higher matrix crack density.

O'Brien [5] suggested a simple closed-form expression for the strain-energy release rate for local delaminations growing uniformly from transverse crack tips. The expression is based on simple load shearing rules and the classical laminated plate theory. It gives the strain energy release rate that depends only on the laminate lay-up and thickness, the location of the cracked ply and subsequent delaminations, the applied load and the laminate width, and is independent of delamination size and matrix crack density. In the nomenclature of this paper it is given by

$$\frac{G^{ld}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2} = \frac{N\hat{E}_x^2 h}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{(N-n)\hat{E}_{ld}} - \frac{1}{N\hat{E}_x} \right) \quad (13)$$

where h is the laminate thickness, N is the number of plies, n is the number of cracked plies, \hat{E}_x and \hat{E}_{ld} are respectively the laminate modulus and the modulus of the locally delaminated sublaminates as calculated from the laminated plate theory. Parameter m has a value of 2 if the cracked ply is in the interior of the laminate, corresponding to local delamination on either side of matrix crack and that of 1 if the cracked ply is a surface ply.

Later, O'Brien [7] showed that this simple closed-form expression is valid for the total strain energy release rate associated with uniform local delamination growing from an angle ply matrix crack. For example, strain energy release rate for local delamination in the $(\theta / -\theta)$ interface of a $[0_2 / \theta_2 / -\theta_2]_s$ laminate with matrix cracks in the $(-\theta)$ -ply is

$$\frac{G^{ld}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2} = \frac{3\hat{E}_x^2 h}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4\hat{E}_{ld}} - \frac{1}{6\hat{E}_x} \right) \quad (14)$$

Since the locally delaminated $[0_2/\theta_2]_T$ sublaminates are asymmetric, the value of \hat{E}_{ld} in Eq. (14) will depend on whether the presence of bending-extension and shear-extension coupling is reflected in the modulus calculation. For all ply orientation angles θ (i.e. from 5° to 90°), the influence of shear-extension coupling on the value of \hat{E}_{ld} and therefore the strain energy release rate was found to be significant. The shear constraint resulted in a greater \hat{E}_{ld} and, hence, correspondingly lower strain energy release rate. However, the effect of bending-extension coupling was proved to be small [7]. It is worth mentioning that in Eqs. (13) – (14), the strain energy release rate is independent from the crack density, since the effect of matrix cracking is not taken into account when calculating the laminate modulus. It is also independent from the crack density. The result of Eq. (14) for a $[0_2/25_2/-25_2]_s$ laminate, for example, is found equal to 21.45 MJ/m^2 and can be reduced to 12.7 MJ/m^2 if shear-extension coupling and bending-extension coupling are taken into account [7]. Still, it is much higher than our predictions, since it does not account for matrix cracking. Comparison of $G^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ values for $[0_2/\theta_2]_s$ laminates, calculated from Eq. (7) and Eq. (14), is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Normalised strain energy release rate $G^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ in $[0_2/\theta_2]_s$ AS4/3506-1 laminates. Crack density $C^{mc} = 1 \text{ crack/cm}$

Angle θ	$G^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 \text{ (MJ/m}^2\text{)}$	
	O'Brien formula, Eq. (14)	Present approach ($D^{ld} = 0$), Eq. (7)
45°	2.331	1.633
60°	1.664	2.363
75°	1.567	2.278
90°	1.589	1.479

Using Eqs. (11) and (12), the contributions of Mode I and Mode II into the total strain energy release rate $G^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ at the onset of local delamination ($D^{ld} = 0$) are estimated for balanced $[0_2/\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$ laminates and plotted in Fig. 4 as a function of the cracked ($-\theta$)-ply orientation angle. It can be seen that $G_I^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ increases monotonically with increasing θ , while $G_{II}^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ reaches a maximum value at approximately $\theta = 50^\circ$. Also, for $[0_2/30_2/-30_2]_s$ and $[0_2/45_2/-45_2]_s$ laminates $G_{II}^{ld} > G_I^{ld}$. Figure 4 suggests that delamination will initiate at relatively low applied strain in a 90° cracked lamina driven mainly by Mode I, while in a 15° cracked lamina will initiate at considerably higher applied strain.

Contributions of Mode I and Mode II into the total strain energy release rate $G^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ at the onset of local delamination ($D^{ld} = 0$) in unbalanced $[0_2/\theta_2]_s$ laminates are plotted in Fig. 5 as a function of the cracked θ -ply orientation angle. It can be seen that $G_I^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ reaches a maximum value at approximately $\theta = 75^\circ$ while $G_{II}^{ld}/\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2$ reaches a maximum value at approximately $\theta = 55^\circ$.

Figure 4. Normalised strain energy release rates $G_I^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (Mode I), $G_{II}^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (Mode II) and $G^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (total) for local delaminations in balanced $[0_2 / \theta_2 / -\theta_2]_s$ AS4/3506-1 laminates as a function of cracked ply orientation angle. Matrix crack density 2 crack/cm, relative delamination area $D^{ld} = 0$ (onset of delamination)

Figure 5. Normalised strain energy release rates $G_I^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (Mode I), $G_{II}^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (Mode II) and $G^{ld} / \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2$ (total) for local delaminations in unbalanced $[0_2 / \theta_2]_s$ AS4/3506-1 laminates as a function of cracked ply orientation angle. Matrix crack density 2 crack/cm, relative delamination area $D^{ld} = 0$ (onset of delamination)

To predict the onset of delamination in an already cracked $[(S) / \phi]_s$ laminate under static loading, a mixed mode fracture criterion can be used

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^M + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^N = 1 \quad (15)$$

where G_{IC} and G_{IIC} are respectively Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughnesses, and M and N are exponents dependent on the material system. For example, for a glass/epoxy system, following [15], the exponents M and N can be taken as $M = 1, N = 2$. Then, to predict cracking onset strains, G_I^{ld} and G_{II}^{ld} values are calculated from Eqs. (11) and (12), and the delamination onset strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}$ can be found as a root of the following equation

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^4 \left(\frac{f_2(D^{ld})}{G_{IIC}}\right)^2 + \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx}^2 \left(\frac{f_1(D^{ld})}{G_{IC}}\right) = 1 \quad \text{when } D^{ld} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Further work is required to validate theoretical predictions. For the lay-ups, damage modes and loading conditions examined in this study the experimental data are currently not available. Under fatigue loading, calculated strain energy release rates together with collected experimental data on damage growth, can be used to identify parameters in the modified Paris law that describes delamination growth. Suitability of Paris law to characterise delamination growth in $[0/90_m]_s$, $m = 2, 4, 6$, cross-ply laminates with transverse matrix cracks has been examined by [16]. Using damage growth predictions, reduction in stiffness can be estimated as a function of the number of fatigue cycles. If the residual stiffness can then be related to both the residual strength and the fatigue life of the specimen, it may become a powerful tool in assessing the reliability of composite materials.

The issue of transition from angle-ply matrix cracking to delamination is not addressed here and is a subject of ongoing research. For transverse cracking in the 90° -ply, energy considerations governing transition to local delamination have been examined in [17, 18].

CONCLUSIONS

Fracture mechanics analysis of crack tip delaminations in composite laminates subjected to in-plane loading is presented and discussed. The equivalent laminate concept is applied to derive expressions for Mode I, Mode II and the total strain energy release rate associated with uniform local delaminations growing from the tips of matrix cracks in the innermost ply of the laminate. These expressions could be used with appropriate fracture criteria to estimate the onset of local delamination in an already cracked off-axis laminate. Comparison with results obtained by O'Brien (1991) shows that O'Brien's closed-form expression for uniform local delamination significantly overestimates the value of the total strain energy release rate leading to lower theoretical strains for the initiation of local delamination and therefore over-conservative designs. Also, it gives the total strain energy release rate as independent of delamination area and does not take into account the cumulative effect of damage.

On the basis of the presented analysis, it is found that strain energy release rate depends linearly on crack density both in balanced $[0_2/\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$ and unbalanced $[0_2/\theta_2]_s$ laminates. The dependence on delamination area is linear in balanced and non-linear in unbalanced laminates. Mode I contribution into the total strain energy release rate increases monotonically with increasing cracked ply orientation angle in balanced $[0_2/\theta_2/-\theta_2]_s$ laminates and reaches a maximum at $\theta = 75^\circ$ in unbalanced $[0_2/\theta_2]_s$ laminates. However, dependence of Mode II contribution on the cracked ply

orientation angle in balanced and unbalanced laminates is similar – it reaches a maximum values at θ between 50° and 55° .

In near future work, the analytical predictions will be compared to numerical (finite element) and experimental data, which for the lay-ups, damage modes and loading conditions examined in this study are currently not available.

REFERENCES

1. Crossman, F.W. and Wang, A.S.D. (1982) The dependence of transverse cracking and delamination on ply thickness in graphite epoxy laminates. In: *Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775*. K.L. Riefsnyder (Ed). ASTM, Philadelphia PA
2. O'Brien, T.K. (1982) Characterization of delamination onset and growth in a composite laminate. In *Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775*. K.L. Reifsnider (Ed). ASTM, Philadelphia PA
3. Takeda, N., and Ogihara, S. (1994) Initiation and growth of delamination from the tip of transverse cracks in CFRP cross-ply laminates. *Composites Science and Technology* 52(3), 309-318
4. Henaff-Gardin, C., Lafarie-Frenot, M.C. and Gamby D. (1996) Doubly periodic matrix cracking in composite laminates Part 2: Thermal biaxial loading. *Composite Structures* 36(1-3): 131-140
5. O'Brien, T.K. (1985) Analysis of local delamination and their influence on composite laminate behavior. In *Delamination and Debonding of Materials, ASTM STP 876*. W.S. Johnson (Ed). ASTM, Philadelphia PA.
6. O'Brien, T.K., and Hooper, S.J. (1991) Local delamination in laminates with angle ply matrix cracks: Part I Tension tests and stress analysis. *NASA Technical Memorandum 104055*
7. O'Brien, T.K. (1991) Local delamination in laminates with angle ply matrix cracks: Part II Delamination fracture analysis and fatigue characterisation. *NASA Technical Memorandum 104076*
8. Salpekar, S.A. and O'Brien T.K. (1993) Analysis of matrix cracking and local delamination in $(0/\theta \text{ theta})_s$ graphite epoxy laminates under tensile load. *ASTM Journal of Composites Technology and Research* 15(2), 95-100
9. Salpekar, S.A., O'Brien, T.K. and Shivakumar K.N. (1996) Analysis of local delaminations caused by angle-ply matrix cracks. *Journal of Composite Materials* 30(4), 418-440
10. Kashtalyan, M., and Soutis, C. (2002) Analysis of local delamination in composite laminates with angle ply matrix cracks. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 39(6), 1515-1537.
11. Zhang, J., Fan, J. and Soutis, C. (1994) Strain energy release rate associated with local delamination in cracked composite laminates. *Composites*, 25(9): 851-862
12. Kashtalyan, M. and Soutis, C. (1999) A study of matrix crack tip delamination and their influence on composite laminate stiffness. *Advanced Composite Letters* 8(4): 149-155
13. Kashtalyan, M. and Soutis C. (2000) The effect of delaminations induced by transverse cracking and splitting on stiffness properties of composite laminates. *Composites Part A* 31(2): 107-119
14. Jones, R.M. (1999) *Mechanics of composite materials: 2nd edition*. Taylor & Francis, Philadelphia PA.
15. Rikards, R., Buchholz, F.G., Wang, H., Bledzki, A.K., Korjakin, A. and Richard, H.A. (1998) Investigation of mixed mode interlaminar fracture toughness of laminated composites by using a CTS type specimen. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 61(3-4), 325-342.
16. Takeda, N., Ogihara, S. and Kobayashi, A. (1995) Microscopic fatigue damage progress in CFRP cross-ply laminates. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 26(12), 859-867.
17. Nairn, J.A., and Hu, S. (1992) The initiation and growth of delaminations induced by matrix microcracks in laminated composites. *International Journal of Fracture* 57(1), 1-24
18. Selvarathinam, A.S. and Weitsman, Y.J. (1999) A shear-lag analysis of transverse cracking and delamination in cross-ply carbon-fibre/epoxy composites under dry, saturated and immersed fatigue conditions. *Composites Science and Technology* 59(14): 2115-2123